

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B506		
Date:	30/01/10		
Take Off:	09:44:54Z	Z	Z
Landing:	15:36:24Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 51 30s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Atlantic/ NW Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voden	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Barrett	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	CVI / Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
9	Mini-LIDAR	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
11	Mission 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 1200 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
Y	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-31	Mo Smith	Initial version
R1			
r2			

B506, 30 Jan 2010 CONSTRAIN FLIGHT 11

Sortie S5: Ice nucleation and secondary ice multiplication in super-cooled Cumulus.

Super-cooled Cumulus are required for observations of mixed-phase studies, where ice nucleation, secondary ice multiplication and warm-rain processes are important. Secondary ice multiplication from splintering during the riming growth of ice particles is active between -3°C and -8°C .

Both the intensity and duration of surface precipitation depends on warm-rain processes (auto-conversion of cloud liquid) and ice-phase processes.

Weather Northerly Airflow over warm sea track

Sortie location

Northwest – Stornoway And The Minch

Sortie summary

Sample a growing Cumulus with a series of ascending straight and level runs.

Alternatively, if there are many Cumulus, sample each by a series of long straight and level runs at specified altitudes.

Cloud penetrations should allow at least 60sec wings level before entering and after leaving cloud to allow for aerosol characterisation

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area (NE point of Lewis) at best-range speed and altitude.
- 2) Define a point A at 58.40W and 5.40W
- 3) **Begin SLR** of 15 Mins Into Wind, LIDAR for Cloud Tops
- 4) **Drop A Sonde** at mid way point, Point B is end of Run
- 5) **Profile descent** (stepped to stay in region, avoiding cloud penetrations) to reach minimum altitude below target clouds.
- 6) **Aerosol characterisation run 500ft below cloud base Define Point C** – ~8 miles East of Point B and Begin return leg down wind for 15 mins to Point D

- 7) **Race track runs between fixed ground points. A,B,C,D.** Runs of 15 minutes in length to sample numerous Cloud Cells. No deviation from SLR. Runs should be aligned roughly along wind. Ascend during turns in 1000ft intervals. Altitudes are from -5°C to -20°C , in particular in the Hallett-Mossop regime -3°C to -8°C ,
- 8) **Deicing Legs** – if icing occurs during a run descend below freezing level. Subsequently ascend to last racetrack level.
- 9) **Stepped Profile Descent through cloud** in a stairwell-fashion profile descent with cloud penetrations at similar altitudes as those on ascent
- 10) **Transit to Prestwick at best range speed and altitude**
- 11) Ascend to Cloud base level (~3kft) and identify growing cumulus.
- 12) **Or Option B: Single Cloud Evolution**
- 13) **B: Cloud penetration runs: Starting at 500ft above cloud base, perform a series of straight and level runs through the cloud oriented along wind, ascending during the turns so that each run is 500ft below cloud top.**

Instrument requirements

Lidar

CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode, except for the sub-cloud run which is in aerosol mode.

Cloud physics to report the time when first ice particles are observed during each of the cloud penetration runs.

Crew:

1. Captain - Alan Foster (Directflight)
2. Co-pilot - Luc Lathouwers (Directflight)
3. CCM - Robbie Voaden (Directflight)
4. Mission Scientist – Paul Barrett (Met Office)
5. Flight Manager - Mo Smith (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics - Martyn Pickering (Met Office)
7. AVAPS - Doug Anderson* (FAAM)
8. Mini-LIDAR / FWVS - Dave Pollard (Met Office)
9. CVI - Kirsty McBeath (Met Office)
10. Manchester Cloud - James Dorsey (University of Manchester)
11. Mission Scientist 2 - Keith Bower (University of Manchester)

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B506

Date: 30 January 2010

Project: CONSTRAIN

Location: NW Scotland

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
084246		Start-Up	0.33 kft	238	55'30.33N, 4'35.86W
093942		ASP	0.32 kft	078	Open
094454		T/O	1.7 kft	265	Prestwick
094817		Video	6.1 kft	263	Start all 4
100101		JW & Nevz	20.0 kft	348	Zero cal
103118	104628	Run 1	20.0 kft	344	
103847		Sonde	20.0 kft	353	Launch #01
104635	110810	Profile 1	20.0 - 0.37 kft	353	50' on QNH 1001mB
110820	111033	Run 2	0.42 - 0.46 kft	157	
110912		Event	0.67 kft	113	climb & turn
111133	112332	Run 2	0.44 - 0.47 kft	339	100', A-B
111850		Heimann	0.44 kft	335	Cal
112447	113628	Run 3	0.86 - 0.92 kft	148	500'
114028	115825	Run 4	4.7 - 4.5 kft	325	4.2k', Q1001
120147	121714	Run 5	5.6 - 5.5 kft	151	5.2k'
122026	123959	Run 6	6.0 kft	340	5.7k' Q1001
124312	125835	Run 7	6.6 kft	157	6.2k'
130212	132152	Run 8.1	7.0 - 7.1 kft	340	6.7k'
132527	133237	Run 8.2	7.1 kft	131	
133238	133915	Run 8.3	7.1 kft	163	
134322	134631	Run 9	8.1 kft	316	7.7k'
135012	135344	Run 10.1	8.6 - 8.5 kft	123	8.2k', Q1001
135722	140115	Run 10.2	8.6 kft	318	
140641	140901	Run 11.1	8.9 kft	116	8.5k'
141418	141714	Run 11.2	8.9 kft	278	
142111	142450	Run 12.1	9.0 - 8.9 kft	108	8.6k'
142802	143300	Run 13	9.3 kft	299	8.9k'
143645	144022	Run 14	9.5 - 9.6 kft	049	9.2k'
144429	144825	Run 15	9.8 - 9.9 kft	288	9.5k'
145224	145655	Run 16	10.1 kft	092	9.7k'
151351		Video	20.0 kft	187	Stop Recording
153624		Land	0.33 kft	213	Prestwick
154019		ASP	0.33 kft	058	on the taxi
154114		Shutdown	0.33 kft	058	55'30.36N, 4'35.86W

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506** Date **30-01-10** Name **P. BARNETT** Page **1** of **12**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
093500					start up
					Lat I.R. shows dark regions as expected
					Expeding wind at 320
					Early T-0
					Climb out - showers visible on horizon
					to port (wind) Area, - high tops
					icing ice in cloud,
					1/8 scattered Cu @ 2000 ft
					- check - Sat I.R. US,
					LIDAR, cloud tops
					NW, JW, Anvil occurrence
					355 A/c winds @ 355 37
					Horace = 351
10:00:00					Transit @ AL 200, showers visible up ahead
101628					showers much more vigorous than yesterday, tops already low ~ 2000 ft
					WINDS - 357, 17
					A/c LEFT 358 37 RIGHT 356 39

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....⁵⁰⁶ Date ..30-01-10 Name P. BARRETT... Page 2 of 12...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1026					Latest visible shows N → cloud
				⊕	development, isolated but numerous showers
				⊕	extensive C _u through broken S _c visually
1029 57					LIDAR - top @ 5000, some breaks.
1031 17	R1	200	343		some development below, but flat S _c ahead
					clouds have developed to left
					LIDAR 8.04H 50% coverage with breaks down to this,
1037					LIDAR Top to 10.5 coverage in sea is
1058 53					SOMDE GONE
					WINDS ARE now 348°
					LIDAR top 6.7, no breaks
					but surface clouds through thinner S _c
1046 36	R1 END 9200				+ sonde in water
	P1				LIDAR - more configurations toward
					edge of sea
					Profile to the left of A-B
					to allow descent through clear
					slit.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....506 Date ..30-01-10 Name P. R. ARNETT Page 3 of 12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Met office RADAR shows
					showers in lines and groups to
					the North of Shetland
112332					Precipitation observed
					below cloud, sun, precip
112810	R2	100	360ish		
1110					SLR @ 110ft
11300					Precip - sun through light
					Passing between two showers
1115					clear now above
					wind dies with height
1120					Cold gust of air from
					showers - off shore region
					wind angle variable but settles on
					330° → 340°
112323	R2				
	R3				SLR @ 800ft
					Heading further East than
					Anticipated - shower
					cloud below about 900ft
113248					mixed phase precip CPI
					Newport A off Cape Wrath
					bed in NW
					possibility of return along
					process back.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...S06...** Date **30-01-10** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **4** of **13**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113708					climbing to in-doubt looking for double heights on the way up, to define first in-doubt leg. BASES 34, Study Main base @ 3.8, 4.0
114028	4	4.2	324	58.48, 5.8	4.2 kft into wind banking in run to rejoin A-B tracks CPI - liquid
114405					ice CPI, low cloud -
1145					on track, ice deleted - laps above by 2000ft
1148					clear gap in cloud, skimmer ahead
1148 30					in cloud, laps just above
1154 23					ice falling from subrail above head
120600		520		59.24, 6.18	Cloud @ 5200
120540					forbance probe begins to ice All cloud = liquid
120507					cloud quite far (or kft) above
1210 07					Pie cap on W/S, some turb. here
121140					cloud laps just above

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506** Date **22-01-12** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **5** of **12**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121305					Cloud ahead of current clear slit
					Cloud physics has minimal icing so good to continue, but turbulence patch is not good anymore.
121447	r5	5200	45	- Seeps	like we have 3 clouds along our run
					unfortunately a fair decision on wind angle so we are tracking diagonally to wind
121600					- starting to glaciate - CPT of ~ 7-8 mm on RADAR just at of cloud now - glanced the edge.
121716	S-comp 5200				RADAR seeing some structure along run.
122021	r6 5700	5700		NORTH DIAGONAL	Run started early - though the shower included. highest intensity core is a couple of miles to the right.
122345					clear cloud ahead - passes RHS of intense core - visually and RADAR

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.506** Date 30-01-10 Name P. BARRETT Page 6 of 12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123116					satellite shows 2 intense showers at southern end of track and of sea long bear gap with smaller shower at Nukunua - thin stratus just below
123547					N S Near cloud top - CPI reporting mixed phase -> only some ice - cloud was 200-300ft above so next - last cell is not analysed
124312	7	6200	Southern Diamond	Diamond 2	Turns prob water
124712					cloud, maintained above the rest large ice crystals
125338					move off a few hundred yards to left to intercept edge of development as given by visual, and RADAR - liquid core precipitating from cloud
	7end				penetrate through cloud close to cloud top, strong RADAR returns precip w/s
	8				icing on probes now upright is liquid surrounded by ice CWI is saturating

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506** Date 30-01-10 Name P. BARRETT Page 7 of 12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130900					Diverting off track using RADAR + USAR to identify updrafts ice buildup now, find an extensive section of cloud
					Coastal - ice at the end of the section.
					3-6mm H ₂ O buildup
					- in Kallet Mossop region @ -12.6°
131200					still on diversion track
					Wind direction difficult to define.
131534					out of cloud
					CU
131929			326		cloud wind ~ 330
					326
					↑
132152	end 81				Stay at same level to get development, no glaciation as yet
					off track but in cloud.
					- following track through previous cells - but track is further to the North
					- looking back now

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.526** Date **30-21-10** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **8** of **12**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1327					Mixed phase, C/I, core near cloud top
1337		7.1	140		Leaving N-S pattern in cloud T = -12.77 Optically thick LIDAR Camera time = 2 minutes before HORACE time.
1344		7.7	320		Wind ~ 300, he MIXED phase
1346					cut off cloud. turn and re-orient to run through cloud along wind, then kept that orientation
					street not necessarily along wind but will sample the street level, winds somewhat variable.
		8.00			less bumps, aligned visually and by RADAR

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506** Date 30-01-10 Name PBARREN Page 9 of 12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140000	10.2	end 82			out of cloud climbing to 8500 cloud in clear region by itself
1405	about 10000				 MAIN: NOW OUT Cloud FROM STREET
1407		8500			CPI - little water CID - small ice turning round into cloud which has decayed somewhat, could be final passage through cloud
1413 SS	1413 SS				about to enter cloud cloud about harder to get cloud developed, new up draughts appeared very close to old location
		8600			
	V7148 - NEW				
	1420 - out		??		NEW
143128	- in old cloud				NEW
					possibly missed "new cell" as we saw it

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506** Date **30-01-10** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **10** of **12**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					- cloud filling in at lower level, harder to spot the new cell as the cell and the street grow
143211		9200			New cell - near the tops
143744	out of cloud				old cell to left
143828	NEW CELL			-	updraft region still, with glaciated sections.
1440	out of cloud				Southern edge of cloud now over land
					T = -16° wind ~330 to NW-Hard
					Cloud moving N-S
					April 144405 heading towards cloud (144532) in OLD cell - high in cloud - CPI - mostly ice still see updraft @ 144636 144644 at of cloud heading
					Layout of OLD to NEW not certain but
					New is at the end of the street - we are using the street as a guide from the far end

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.506** Date **30-01-10** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **11** of **12**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144730	- in cell				through into New cell via other growing cell
					climbing east and aligning to the street for next run
145314					heading for original turret still growing, still trying to find around
145508					- old turret - geographic split now?
145600					long time in darkness
145622					out of dark
145655	16				end of run east of Street.
					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> T=0 T=1 T=2 T=3 </div>
9.0					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> </div>
8.0					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> </div>
7.0					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> </div>
6.0					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> </div>
5.0					<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> </div>

B506 07:40:15-15:42:05

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

Time	Flight level	Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv	Nominally 34000 Hz	Nominally 7.5 Torr	Nominally 35 - 40 °C
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
01/29/2010 11:57:56	Previous Flight	60.072	32309.10	N/A	N/A
01/30/2010 09:30:06	Pre-Flight/Gnd	68.865	34570.00	7.51	35.50
10:00:22	FL200	66.635	34051.67	7.10	35.42
10:06:10	FL200	65.761	33941.17	7.06	35.43
10:43:41	FL200	64.617	33358.50	7.07	35.53
11:11:15	100 ft	63.077	33483.46	7.53	35.55
12:04:42	FL052	62.319	32727.83	7.53	37.93
13:04:47	6700 ft	60.028	32312.43	7.53	39.58
13:45:03	7700 FT	59.610	32140.53	7.51	40.10
14:52:58	9700 FT	60.875	32561.07	7.50	38.13
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv)	: _____			
NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	: _____			
Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	: _____			
CO Calibrations on automatic repeat?	: YES/NO	Interval set?	: 40 mins	
<p>co tIME SYNCH 07:19:03 co zERO VALV EON 08:39:18 - 08:56:10</p>				

Cloud Physics Flight Log B506

Date:30/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:07:00:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.04	Vref (>7V):	7.72	El#1 V (>1):	0.6	El#1 V (>1):	24.72	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-2.1
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.2	El#32 V (>1):	2.32	El#32 V (>1):	2.85	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-1.8
			Sheath flow	14.09	El#64 V (>1)	0.86	El#64 V (>1)	1.95				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
07:38:48			15									
07:40:11			20									
07:41:28			30									
07:43:02			40									
07:45:25				ZERO								
10:31:18	FL200											Start Run 1
10:32:00				25							Noise	
10:34:00				Noise?							Noise	
10:36:00				45							Noise	
10:38:00				5							Noise	
10:40:00				15							Noise	
10:42:00				10							Noise	
10:44:00				25							Noise	
10:46:00				20	0.3							
10:46:33	FL200			25								End of Run 1 & Start Profile 1
10:47:24	FL190			40								

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
10:48:39	FL180			20								
10:49:59	FL170			50								
10:51:09	FL160			35								
10:52:07	FL150			40								
10:53:03	FL140			25								
10:54:13	FL130			2								
10:55:15	FL120			1								
10:56:06	FL110			2								
10:56:58	FL100			1								
10:58:00	FL090			1								
10:59:06	FL080			3								
10:59:57	FL070			4							Noise	
11:01:01	FL060			2							Noise	
11:01:57	FL050			10							Noise	
11:02:51	FL040			10							Noise	
11:03:46	FL030			30		0.0004		1	800	8	0.1	
11:04:42	FL020			25							0.1	
11:06:09	FL010			30							Noise	
11:08:08	50'											End of Profile
11:08:20	100'											Start Run 2
11:09:00				25								
11:11:00				25		0.0003		1		1	0.1	
11:13:00				25		0.0003		1			0.1	
11:15:00				25							Noise	
11:17:00				25							Noise	
11:19:00				25							Noise	
11:21:00				25							Noise	
11:23:30												End of Run
11:24:52	500'											Start Run 3
11:25:00				25							Noise	
11:27:00				25							Noise	
11:29:00				25							Noise	
11:31:00				25							Noise	
11:33:00				40		0.0008		2	800	1/8	Noise	
11:35:00				40		0.0008		5	800	1		
11:36:40												End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
11:40:32	4200'											Start Run 4
11:41:00		16	10	35		0.0001		1			70	
11:44:00		14	25	200		0.0225		10	25	12	350	
11:46:00				30								
11:48:00				25								
11:50:00		28	30	100		0.01		9	500	8	500	
11:52:00				12								
11:54:00				15								
11:56:00				15								
11:58:25												End of Run
12:01:47	5200'											Start Run 5
12:02:00		15	30	15		0.001		3	100	12	1200	
12:04:00				2								
12:08:00		10	20	50		0.06		200	800	8	200	
12:10:00		10	35	300		0.14		200	125	11	1200	
12:12:00		20	25	18				50	25	12	200	
12:14:00				5								
12:16:00		10	35	50		0.08		50	800	8	200	
12:17:16												End of Run
12:20:24	5500'											Start Run 6
12:21:00				5								
12:23:00				4								
12:25:00				3								
12:27:00		35	30	3		0.03		20	800	8	100	
12:29:00		10	25	10		0.04		6	800	8	100	
12:31:00				2								
12:33:00		15										
12:35:00		5	30	45				30	800	1/8	20	
12:37:00				10								
12:39:00				10								
12:40:00												End of Run 6
12:43:10	6200'											Start Run 7
12:44:00				1								
12:46:00				1								
12:48:00		25	25			0.03		50	400	1/8	1000	
12:50:00		25	25	300		0.06		50	50	12	1200	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
12:52:00				3								
12:54:00				1								
12:56:00		1		2		0.05		9	800	8	10	
12:58:00				2								
12:58:35												End of run
13:02:13	6700'											Start Run 8.1
13:03:00				4								
13:05:00				15								
13:07:00				5								
13:09:00		15										
13:11:00		5	45	300		0.06		500	800	1/8	200	
13:13:00				2								
13:15:00		10	40	10		0.0001		500	100	12	400	
13:17:00				1								
13:19:00				7								
13:21:00		30	40	150		0.05		800	800	9	1200	
13:21:53												End of Run
13:25:24	6700											Start Run 8.2
13:26:00		1	45	500		0.1		800	800	8	400	
13:28:00				5								
13:30:00				5								
13:32:00				5								
13:32:33												End of Run 8.2 & Start Run 8.3?
13:33:00				10								
13:35:00				5								
13:37:00		1	30	5		0.07		1000	50	12	1000	
13:39:00				2								
13:39:17												End of Run
13:43:22	7700											Start Run 9
13:44:00				1								
13:46:00		2	35	1		0.02		500	800	9	200	
13:46:31												End of Run
13:50:11	8200'											Start Run 10.1
13:51:00				3								
13:52:00		15	40			0.02		500	800	8	700	
13:53:34												End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
13:57:20	8200'											Start Run 10.2
13:58:00				3								
14:00:00		10	35	60		0.12		200	800	8	200	
14:01:13												End of Run
14:06:43	8500'											Start Run 11.1
14:07:00		2	35	160		0.02		50	800	8	50	
14:09:01												End of run
14:14:00	8500'											Start Run 11.2
14:15:00		2	40	300		0.2		500	800	8	250	
14:17:14												End of Run
14:21:11	8600'											Start Run 12
14:22:00		20	35	10		0.09		1000	800	1/8	300	
14:24:00				5								
14:24:50												End of run
14:28:00	8900'											Start Run 13
14:29:00		5										
14:31:00		0.1	45	20		0.02		500	600	1/8	350	
14:33:00												End of run
14:36:45	9200'											Start Run 14
14:37:00				5								
14:39:00		2	45	180		0.15		200	800	8	10	
14:40:22												End of run
14:44:41	9500'											Start Run 15
14:45:00				2								
14:47:00		2	30	90		0.25		100	800	1/8	70	
14:48:23												End of Run
14:52:23	9700'											Start Run 16
14:53:00				7								
14:55:00		4	50	8		0.1		500	800	8	20	
14:56:56												End of Run

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B506

Date: 30 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. Network hung pre-flight. LEDs on Hub and Switch at Fwd Core Console flashing at same regular rate.
3. HORACE crashed at same time as network hung. Restarted HORACE and recording. IE windows have no data, no time etc. Stop all processes but sill has about 20 H_SERVE_BGnnnn jobs running. Shutdown HORACE from system menu and restart after resetting network switch power. Came up okay.
4. Network - Reset power at fwd CC switch,
5. Pyrgeometers – Upper noisy
6. Turb probe – Attack diff signal offset by ~ 30mb, prob due to icing at 1150. SS Diff went at 1211, AoA check at 1220,
7. WxRx – Stabilisation fault shown on rear display, (ok on cockpit unit). Also, Snagit occasionally stops capturing radar images. Restart then okay.
8. Cloud probes – all with about 2 cms ice build up
- 9.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS – 17 x satpics, KB

Satcom H – not used

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Flight: Latest

Key :

	Not Fitted		Not Operated		Ok
	Unusable Data		Minor Problems		

[back](#)

Primary Systems

	Temperature	Remote Sensing	Cloud Physics
AMTG	Cabin Temperature	ARIES	2DC
AVAPS	Heimann	BBR (clear) Lower	2DP
Cabin Pressure Rmount	Rosemount DIT	BBR (clear) Upper	2DS
Camera - Downward Facing	Rosemount NDIT	BBR (IR) Lower	ADA
Camera - Forward Facing	Hygrometry	BBR (IR) Upper	CAPS
Camera - Rearward Facing	Buck CR2	BBR (red) Lower	CDP (Canister)
Camera - Upward Facing	FWVS	BBR (red) Upper	CDP (Fuselage)
Cruciform GPS	General Eastern	CASI/ATM	CIP 100
DLU AERACK	SAW Hygrometer	DEIMOS	CIP 25
DLU BBR Lower	Total Water Probe	IR Camera	CPI
DLU BBR Upper		JNO2 Photometer Lower	FFSSP
DLU Core Chem		JNO2 Photometer Upper	FFSSP Computer
DLU Core Consoles		JO1D Photometer Lower	FSSP (UMan)
DLU Port Aft		JO1D Photometer Upper	INC
DLU Port Fwd		LIDAR	Johnson Williams
DLU Stbd Fwd		MARSS	Nevzorov
Fax machine		Mini-LIDAR	PADS Computer
GIN Applanix POSAV510		SHIMS Lower	SEADAS Computer
HORACE		SHIMS Upper	SID1
INU Honeywell H423		SWS	SID2
Printer		TAFTS	SID3

RVSM Static Pressure	
S9 Static Press Rmount	
Satcom Data	
Satcom Phones	
Turb Diff Centre- Static	
Turb Diff Left-Right	
Turb Diff Up-Down	
Turb Horizontal Check	
Turb Vertical Check	
Weather Radar	
XR5 GPS	

File View Window Help

Start [Icons]

Channel: #faam146

*** FAAM_MS3 [GLUXE@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

*** Mode change [+nt] on #faam146 by photon.cas.manchester.ac.uk

*** MetoCLee [vircuser@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

<MetoCLee> Hi Mo

[FAAM_MS3] hello Clare its Keith

[FAAM_MS3] Mo would like an update from Exeter for conditions at Cranfield on Tuesday

<MetoCLee> We were just looking at that and talking to Pete re all the options.

<MetoCLee> Pete is finding out about the firecover at Cranfield.

<MetoCLee> We can't see your position reports.

<MetoCLee> Weather in Cranfield should be rainy with max 7 deg. I don't think there is a snow issue.

[FAAM_MS3] OK will tell Mo

*** FAAM_Woolley [Wooli@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

<FAAM_Woolley> bonjour

[FAAM_MS3] bonjour - wcheck other things on FAAM website - we are sendingt Position reports so maybe a BADC thing

<MetoCLee> Position reports OK.

<MetoCLee> Sorry fot he bad typing

<MetoCLee> Can you see the sat pic OK?

<MetoCLee> Richard says stick with the plan.

[FAAM_MS3] I just got the 10am of the met office website now - are you sending any?

<MetoCLee> No

[FAAM_MS3] conditions much better today - turrets goibg up to approx FL200! Sticking to plan - 60nm N-S runs

<MetoCLee> Richard says excellent! And is very excited and arm wavey!!

[FAAM_MS3] doing FL200 run and sonde in 3 mins

[FAAM_MS3] Mo says she just received the weather report

<FAAM_Woolley> good stuff

[FAAM_MS3] message to Peter - please arrange room for Gaynor - because of Sci flts Sun, Moi and transit Tuesday. booking not done yet. Ta

*** Server connection lost

*** Nickname is already in use: FAAM_MS3

*** Server connection lost

*** Server connection lost

*** Nickname is already in use: FAAM_MS3

@FAAM_MS3
FAAM_Woolley
MetoCLee

1 [1] connecting 2 [1] #faam146

Channel: #faam146 - No topic set

FAAM_MS3
FAAM_Woolley
MetoCLee

*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[FAAM_MS3] back online - lost comms during P1 to 50ft#
<FAAM_Woolley> hello
[FAAM_MS3] did you get previous message to Pete?
<FAAM_Woolley> "[11:13:14] FAAM_Woolley: have passed on the Gaynor message to pc"
<FAAM_Woolley> I guess you were offline
[FAAM_MS3] thanks - yess I lost it!!
**** Server connection lost
**** Server connection lost
**** Server connection lost
**** Server connection lost

FAAM_MS3
FAAM_Woolley
MetoCLee

*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
 [FAAM_MS3] ok lost comms again til now - did I miss anything important?
 [FAAM_MS3] Runs on line going through 3 cells in NE only liquid, in SW glaciating - great stuff !!
 [FAAM_MS3] middle cloud is collection of cells going NW 6kft 1st cell only water, 2nd only ice

**** Server connection lost
 **** Server connection lost

FAAM_MS3
FAAM_Woolley
MetoCLee

*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
 <FAAM_Woolley> you're back?
 [FAAM_MS3] sorry lost comms til 1409
 <FAAM_Woolley> hey ho
 <FAAM_Woolley> everyone else is at lunch
 [FAAM_MS3] ok any news - its going really well up here
 <FAAM_Woolley> Plans for tomorrow basically the same as today from what I hear
 <FAAM_Woolley> Are you looking good for being back at 1530?
 [FAAM_MS3] yes
 <MetoCLee> Any icing?
 <MetoCLee> Debrief in hotel?
 **** Server connection lost
 **** Server connection lost
 **** Server connection lost
 **** Server connection lost
 [FAAM_MS3] Quite a bit of icing ~30mm - no de-icing . will ask about debrief

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 30.01.10 Flight No: B 506 Pre-Flighter: Steve Cowan

No. ↓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up			
1	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
2	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	
3	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBS made	
8	Fore CorCon	CBS made, PCs ON	
9	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	HORACE	Recording data	
11	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	Nevozorov	Checked and OFF	
15	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	FWWS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	GPS (XREM)	Checked	
23	Satcom C	Checked	
24	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	<i>NOT FITTED</i>
25	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	CGPS	CBS and PC ON	
29	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No. ↓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	CCN SS coils A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36	Core Chemistry	O ₂ /NO ₂ /CO zeros performed OK	

External Checks			
No. ↓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
37	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	Nevozorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	All other covers	Removed	

Avalon Checks			
No. ↓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
49	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	
50	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51	Tools	Avalon Informed	
52	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	
53	ICEX	Applied	
54	Turb Probe	Traps emptied, detail contents -	

Signed

**** Check no butanol ****

a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1400 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1300 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1400 UTC

Range corrected signal - 48 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 108 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 126 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Time after midnight (minutes)

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2500356 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2505974 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2511375 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
 IN KNOTS FOR DISTANCE AT 4 MIN INTERVALS
 POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

Met Office

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ISSUED BY WAFC UKMO/LONDON
WIND/TEMPERATURE
FL 050
VALID 12 UTC 31 JAN 10
BASED ON 06 UTC DATA ON 31 JAN 2010
Units used: knots; degrees Celsius
Temperatures negative
unless prefixed by '+'
Generated by Aero Weather - www.iblsoft.com

1000 on Sat 30 Jan

1030 on Sat 30 Jan

1100 on Sat 30 Jan

1130 on Sat 30 Jan

1200 on Sat 30 Jan

1230 on Sat 30 Jan

1330 on Sat 30 Jan

1400 on Sat 30 Jan

